

Deliverable D1.3 A pan-European model for data management in life sciences

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents a sustainable and scalable operating model for harmonised data management in European projects. The model itself is a set of recommendations and best practices in data management applicable in European projects, guaranteeing an overall harmony in data management practice. The model is targeted mainly at data managers and data stewards to assist researchers in offering advice on responsible management approaches in research projects in

life-science domains. Nevertheless, it is also dedicated to principal investigators as a guide introducing the main aspects of data management necessary for good management practice.

The preparation of the operating model was carried out in two main phases. A formulation of the Draft description of pan-European model for coordinated data management in life sciences represents the outcome of the first phase and is captured in a milestone “M1.2 Draft description of pan-European model for coordinated data management in LS”. The drafted model was further elaborated within WP1 and in collaboration with WP3. The final version of the operating model reflects outcomes from other Tasks of WP1 which evolved in the course of the project in parallel with the presented operating mode.

This document covers an applied methodology, a definition of prerequisites necessary for a general operating model applicable in projects and, most importantly, the operating model itself, which is defined as a procedure of several consecutive steps that should be taken into consideration and properly addressed by those supporting European research projects, with the aim to deliver a responsible data management practice vital for sound research and innovation ecosystem.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	Yes
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	Yes

Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes
Key Result 3.4: Enable ‘FAIR at source’ practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No

<p>Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.</p>	<p>No</p>
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3. Introduction

This deliverable aims to present the operating model for harmonised data management in life sciences applicable in European projects. The model itself is a set of recommendations and implemented best practices in the data management process. The operating model can be implemented Europe-wide and secures an overall harmony in data management practice. In a context of this deliverable, the word harmonisation represents, at first, the coherence of processes applicable on data management in specific, country-dependent scientific environments, while reflecting the general EU approach to data management. Secondly, the harmonisation of data management (DM) occurs on two levels:

- harmonisation of proposed DM according to the EU requirements;
- harmonisation of proposed DM with regards to the specific scientific areas and/or communities.

The presented operating model includes both above mentioned aspects. In addition, the model itself and its dissemination presupposes a utilisation of a common terminology established by the Data Management Network to ensure overall compliance with the established best practices.

The operating model was created in collaboration with the Data Management Network (established within Task 1.1, WP1) and originates from outcomes of Best Practices (D1.1, D1.4), brokering models (Task 1.2, WP1) and business models (Task 1.3, WP1) in the respective parts. Similarly, the model was inspired by the formulated best practices in data management presented in the [Research Data Management toolkit for Life Sciences](#)¹ (RDMkit) (WP3). Dissemination of the existing operating model and creation of suitable training materials are foreseen in the forthcoming months (WP2).

4. Methodology

4.1 Data collection on data management processes in ELIXIR Nodes

An initial phase of the creation of the harmonised model was based on an analysis of information on the requirements of the European Commission for data management and the already existing approaches in individual ELIXIR Nodes.

The model background therefore builds on up-to-date requirements on data management plans for projects funded by the EU’s research and innovation framework programme Horizon Europe, in which the preparation of data management plans became mandatory and, more specifically, on individual experiences of principal investigators of European projects.

¹<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

A survey was launched with the aim to identify current practice in data management in running European projects, specifically focusing on utilisation of existing IT infrastructures. A summary of approaches led to the formulation of data management prerequisites which were essential for the initial conceptual framework of the harmonised operating model. The major part of the gathered feedback showed a heterogeneity of approaches by principal investigators and, at the same time, reflected different stages of preparedness to address the data management issue.

The results of the survey also showed better awareness of data management in those cases where a particular ELIXIR Node participated in the formulation of a data management plan. A strong emphasis on the systematic and comprehensive data management was obvious in those projects in which researchers used the ELIXIR infrastructure, its services, tools, or computational and data core resources. In such cases, the data management plans were partially or fully tailored on the list of tools for the preparation of the data management plans which later resulted in the comprehensive approach provided by the [RDMkit](#)².

4.2 Draft description of pan-European model for coordinated data management in life sciences

This deliverable builds on the [M1.2 Draft description of pan-European model for coordinated data management in life sciences](#)³ which was submitted in July 2022. The draft introduced the concept of the harmonised data management operating model which was shared within WP1 for further development. The draft was reviewed and recommendations and outputs of simultaneously developing tasks and work packages were incorporated.

An important part of the model shaping processes was the periodic teleconference calls of WP1 as well as the communication of the progress with other WPs – namely WP3, WP2 and WP4. The draft description showed the utilisation of existing know-how and its interconnection which anticipated that the data management process could be divided into logical steps which, despite diversities resulting from legal frameworks of individual European countries, could be taken as a general approach. This led to a conclusion that the operation model is not intended to be exhaustive, but rather should offer a general recommendation for offering services for good data management, data reproducibility, and data reuse applicable to diverse national environments.

The essence of this process relied on Task 1.1 of WP1 – the establishment of a European expert network of data managers and data stewards. The network connects national data centres and infrastructures and drives the development of interoperable solutions taking into account international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

There are two main facts which need to be taken into consideration. Firstly, an important role of data management experts lies in the decision to recommend storage of data in open-access repositories, such as the [ELIXIR Deposition Databases for Biomolecular Data](#)⁴. The open-access repositories allow

²<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

³<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1GBZIBnRKiTTW9QGfkdPTSiGFUZ6VLdo2>

⁴<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

immediate and permanent access to the research results, so anyone can download, analyse and use the data. Secondly, the brokering of data to these repositories that Task 1.2 is dedicated to map, analyse, and prototype brokering models. During the evolution of the presented operating model, it was concluded that data brokering stands outside the scope of this general model and will be the focus of a separate report.

4.3 Anchoring of the model in the context of data management best practices

The D1.4 ELIXIR Best Practices recommendations deliverable represents an anchor of the harmonised operating model presented in this document. Both this deliverable and D1.4 were developed in parallel and illustrate the flow of the knowledge within WP1. The aim of the deliverable D1.4 was capturing, collating, and disseminating the collective data management expertise that resides across the ELIXIR member Nodes. It can be taken as a comprehensive upgrade of the Data Collection on Data Management Processes in ELIXIR Nodes as described above in section 4.1.

The deliverable D1.4 provides guidelines focusing on promotion the knowledge sharing and capacity building among the ELIXIR member Nodes when it comes to data management, as well as harmonising the guidance across Nodes while, at the same time, taking into account the local conditions. It should also help with identifying and prioritising data management training needs and the development of training material (WP2) and documented best practice (WP3). Furthermore, this resource should highlight how the ELIXIR services can solve data management issues for the research community. The work of establishing best practice guidelines to a great extent interacts with the work done in WP2 Training, WP3 Toolkit, and WP5 Demonstrators. It was decided that the primary target audience for the guideline content should be the professionals in a research-supporting data steward role. The emerging [RDMkit](#) web resource designed and established by WP3 was selected as the medium for disseminating the best practice guidelines content.

In summary, the importance of the D1.4 for the D1.3 – it was the whole process of mutual coordination for various aspects of data management which were, to some extent, anticipated by the needs formulated in the final harmonised data management model.

4.4 Creation of the operating model

The process of model creation evolved in several phases, combining utilisation of information and data from other tasks of WP1, together with outcomes of WP3, WP2 and WP5. The first important phase was reached by the conceptualization of the harmonised data management model, based on information from the related surveys and the interaction with WP4 where impact was taken into account.

The following phase included the implementation of the so-called Data Life Cycle in the data management operating model and harvesting know-how contained in the [RDMkit](#).

The most important part of the [RDMkit](#) utilisation lies in proper guidance towards the creation of a data management plans, which represents, in a certain way, the most powerful approach to data management. The [RDMkit](#) recommends several online tools that help researchers to create the data

management plan. Among other tools, a use of the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#)⁵ (DSW) is strongly recommended. The DSW was developed and continues to be maintained by ELIXIR, it represents a complex solution for the preparation of data management plan, and also allows an application of a knowledge model that meets requirements of the EU's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe. On top of that, use of the DSW is officially recommended by the [Horizon Europe Programme Guide](#)⁶.

The final stage of the model creation incorporated the feedback from members of the Data Management Expert Network gathered during ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP1 & WP8/9 F2F meeting in Padua, Italy, which took place in September 2022.

As already mentioned, the proposed operating model is based on best practices guidelines for data management formulated by WP1 in collaboration with WP3 which are presented in the [RDMkit](#). The model comprises of three main steps:

- Examination of data problems with data experts and preparation of a data management plans;
- Ensuring access to technical facilities;
- Consideration of data management costs.

5. Results: A pan-European model for coordinated data management in life sciences

5.1 Description of current practice regarding utilised data management models at ELIXIR Nodes

Data management is an important aspect of any research in the life sciences. There is a clear necessity to approach data produced within European research projects thoughtfully, following the example of the framework programmes Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. Data management plans became an integral part of projects funded by Horizon Europe. The growing importance of EOSC implementation into the national research environments provides another unifying point for the hitherto very heterogeneous data management approaches in Europe.

Most of the current approaches towards data management are based on collaborative projects dedicated to creating a field oriented model, usually based on a knowledge model of the respective field. Various resources are already available to create data management plans (e.g. DSW, DMPOne etc.) which is the first important step of data management. Remarkable contribution of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project lies in the collection of know-how, best practices and also definition of a common data management terminology which is available in the [RDMkit](#).

⁵<https://ds-wizard.org/>

⁶<https://www.google.com/search?client=firefox-b-d&q=horizon+europe+programme+guide>

It is important to take into account diversities resulting from different legal frameworks of individual European countries. The operation model thus does not have an objective to be exhaustive, it more likely offers a general recommendation for good data management, data reproducibility, and data reuse applicable for diverse national environments.

Focusing on the data reproducibility and reuse, selection of an appropriate repository is vital. It is possible to store data in an open-access repository, such as one of the [ELIXIR Deposition Databases for Biomolecular Data](#)⁷, or to use other publicly available repositories, e.g. Zenodo.

5.2 Prerequisites of general operation model for Europe

5.2.1 Personnel and field expertise - expert network, best practice (Task 1.1)

Scientists in general are currently not trained in data management, but mainly in their own fields of expertise. They gather only slowly the necessity of data management in research practice from their peers. Hence, data management habits come slowly from the experiences scientists collect and they are not the same in each science field.

In order to achieve the highest quality of data management, coordinated and experienced data managers from various subfields are needed to set up and comply with the international standards. ELIXIR infrastructure can serve as a hub for such a data management expert network as it spans across multiple life science subfields and it is dedicated to data interoperability and training.

In Task 1.1, the Data Management Expert Network was created, bringing together the data management community from across ELIXIR. The network focuses on capturing, collating and disseminating the collective data management expertise that resides across the ELIXIR member Nodes. To this end, the network is developing guidelines that support knowledge sharing and capacity building in data management, and seeks to harmonise data management guidance in ELIXIR Nodes. The best practice guidelines and implementation of the best practice across Nodes is closely linked to the work done in the other work packages of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project.

To help train new data managers, a subgroup from the expert network gathered during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project regularly analyses individual areas of data management, provides best practices (e.g. data documentation, identifiers, etc.) and updates the [RDMkit](#) knowledge base accordingly. In collaboration with WP2, the subgroup assists in data management training and capacity building events.

5.2.2 Data resources, Data access and Data distribution

To harmonise the process of data management at pan-european level across all the ELIXIR Nodes, some important and particular resources should be available and synchronised. Most importantly, the

⁷<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

FAIR ecosystem must be in place and its elements should be easy to implement. The basis of reasonable data management lies in the synchronicity of data archives, system of authorization and authentication of data and computational resources, and, last but not least, existing system of repositories with guaranteed sustainability. The data resources show a variety of proveniences spanning institutional or laboratory data to ELIXIR Core Data Resources used as standards for certain fields. Responsible data management includes an implemented metadata structure according to discipline standards and makes that utilisation of data for analysis and interpretation more comprehensive.

Brokering of data to repositories facilitates the arrival of data with high levels of FAIR compliance into the global pool of life science data, while FAIR compliance ensures its movement through this ecosystem, with each data resource adding value and reaching new audiences. In addition, data brokering can provide an important tool during the operation term of a scientific project, supporting the smooth flow of data between distributed groups generating data, those operating computational analysis, and the end users responsible for interpretation.

5.2.3 Data management and data stewardship services

At the current status of investigation it is possible to clearly highlight several trends which could serve as advice for the implementation and harmonisation of data management and/or data stewardship (DM/DS) services within the different ELIXIR Nodes. This is also applicable for other organisations providing DM/DS services, either in fields within the research community other than the life-sciences or outside of research institutions.

5.2.3.1 DM/DS services provision

In the majority of ELIXIR Nodes, DM/DS services are provided to the research community through a wide range of activities addressing research and innovation staff's most common needs in terms of data management and stewardship.

Services most commonly offered to the community are:

- DMP tools and consultation (Data Stewardship Wizard, DMPOnline..)
- DM/DS best practice guidelines, usually addressed in dedicated websites;
- Consultancy services to guide users facing the implementation of FAIR/Open data principles for the first time;
- Dedicated IT infrastructure for DM/DS. The implementation of these services usually includes access to IT resources such as data storage, high performance computing resources and computational pipelines. In a case of more advanced deployment, IT resources are offered to users in the form of tool assemblies which provide instruments to cover several steps of the research data lifecycle concatenating different resources in a single platform;
- Training, often delivered through courses covering the different aspects of FAIR/Open data principles implementation.

If an ELIXIR Node doesn't provide DM/DS services to the community then capacity building activities and know-how transfer are the necessary steps towards harmonisation of DM/DS approaches. This could be realised via available ELIXIR instruments, such as staff exchange, training, or implementation studies dedicated to capacity building in close connection with the outcomes of WP2.

5.2.3.2 Funding

Funds supporting the provision of DM/DS services usually come from different sources.

Three major sources of funding were identified during the survey performed by Task 1.3 of WP1:

- Dedicated national grants - most of the current DM/DS services are supported by national funding via grant agencies or research ministries;
- Dedicated EU grants - a relevant number of DM/DS services are supported as part of EU funded projects;
- The institutional budget - in a relevant number of cases, costs generated by the provision of DM/DS services are covered by the institution's own budget.

In the vast majority of cases, the provision of services is not supported by an exclusive single source of financing but by combination of the three sources listed above.

A potential reason for having multiple sources of income supporting DM/DS related activities could be the fact that, in most cases, a Node provides a plethora of DM/DS activities, where the relevant underlying costs like personnel, hardware and training, are usually not fully reflected in the project plan. As a result, a small but still significant amount of the costs for DM/DS services is not covered and these activities are provided in part or in full as an "in-kind" contribution.

Eventually, in a very limited number of cases, Nodes are moving towards a cost-recovery model where the costs are charged to the end users. The last option seems to be implemented temporarily in order to move towards a more sustainable model for the provision of DM/DS services, rather than applied as a stable source of income.

5.2.3.3 Service sustainability via a DM/DS Community

The survey so far has shown that, in the vast majority of cases, the DM/DS services in their current implementation are expected to be "likely sustainable" for the future time frame. It should be highlighted that this forecast is based only on the Nodes' considerations of the financial sustainability of the service, not on an accurate financial analysis of the current costs and incomes. Interestingly, those Nodes with a long history of provision of services are moving towards a model where costs are charged to the end users.

The character of DM/DS services provided by an Infrastructure varies significantly depending on parameters of national/international calls. If significant effort should be needed to perform DM/DS activities, one of logical solutions lies in the possibility to include costs for DM/DS in the project budget and prevent offering it as "in kind" or infrastructure service with no cost. It is therefore

desirable for DM/DS in EU projects to get recommendations for such a solution and clearly define rules for budgeting of such service.

One of the critical elements in sustainability of services is the Network of experts established in ELIXIR-CONVERGE which at this stage is solely funded by the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. Reflecting the importance of DM in ELIXIR strategy, there is movement towards initiation of ELIXIR Community for Data Management which would be funded via ELIXIR budget. Sustaining such a DM/DS community via ELIXIR which is currently founded by ELIXIR-CONVERGE is an excellent opportunity to further develop DM/DS strategy and its implementation. This will be remarkable steps towards a stable Data Management environment and key personnels funding able to coordinate DM at national level and guaranteeing sustainability of builded DM ecosystem. Consequently, reflecting EOSC pan-European activity and its implementation at national levels, the sustainability of DM services should be an integral part of the EOSC implementation anticipating the model of distributed resources allocated for DM.

5.3 The harmonised data management model

A pan-European model for data management in life sciences takes into account the complexity of data management plans as well as their harmonisation. We suggest the model as a procedure guaranteeing harmonisation of steps and utilisation of tools and know-how developed during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. The procedure can be characterised by consecutive steps reflecting the ELIXIR developed strategies, tools and resources, and if applicable, also the readiness of the national environment towards data management.

The model procedure is as follows:

- The expert network and national data management hubs as the basic elements of data management process;

This establishes personnel authorities as well as scientific centres providing assistance in data management plan preparation. The outcome is reflected in synchronisation of services, identification of tools and resources and model of sustainability

- Consulting services to analyse project plans and data stewardship strategies - a step towards realisation;

Involvement of key experts and trained personnels will guarantee that the data management plans of projects are aligned with project plans according to the best practices and national requirements. The creation of data management plans reflects complexity of the project and ELIXIR recommended tools for data management plan guarantees its utilisation.

- Recommended ELIXIR data management tools - harmonised approach for data management plan and data management;

The [RDMkit](#) provides easy access to a curated collection of research data management guidelines, best practices, tools, and services. We strongly encourage researchers to use the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#), allowing creation of smart data management plans for FAIR open science.

- Data storage, data access, open science - operational cost and financial strategy;

A key element in a data management plan is localization of IT resources including existing computational resources and repositories. The model takes into account various strategies and resources availability which serve as a qualified estimation of cost. A detailed process towards the data access as well as applicable licence conditions and data policy must be defined. Possible overlap with EOSC shall be also provided.

- Activity based funding approach of data management and financial security;

Based on surveys launched within WP1 (deliverable D1.2, Task 1.4) and best practices over ELIXIR Nodes, the only sustainable solution is that the DM/DS services will be provided as an eligible cost of scientific projects. In such a case, a research infrastructure will be the service provider which makes possible not only sustainability but also scalability.

6. Conclusions

This document summarises the evolution of the pan-European model for coordinated data management in life sciences. The final version arose from the draft description presented in July 2021 and elaborates on the pre-defined prerequisites addressing necessary expertise, data resources, data management and data stewardship services and options of respective funding. Besides, the model incorporates or reflects outcomes from other WP1 Tasks, which were achieved alongside the preparation of this deliverable, in particular, recommendations of best practices in data management, business models and brokering. The model is thus a result of joint efforts and existing interconnections among WP1 and WP3. It is foreseen that, as the next step, the operating model will be made publicly available and suitable ways of its dissemination will be explored.

7. Impact

An impact of the work can be identified at numerous levels of the data management process at the ELIXIR Nodes and, more importantly, in its dissemination over EU institutions dealing with EU's requirements on data management. The suggested model is represented as the recommended procedure which is deeply anchored in the [RDMkit](#) which provides all necessary information about the particular steps of the procedure.

The data management model is conceptually based on achievements of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project and relies primarily on the established Data Management Expert Network. Tight collaboration of experts and their contribution to the [RDMkit](#) guarantees robust background for

further development and flexible adaptation on specific requirements which can be dictated by national conditions. Last but not least the process is robustly builded on existing ELIXIR Deposition Databases. Harmonisation of data management prerequisites and components including training activities has already led to an initiative for establishment of an ELIXIR Data Management Community. The Establishment of an ELIXIR Data Management Community would provide sustainability for the outcomes of ELIXIR-CONVERGE through funded activities, and create a focal point for coordinated data management actions across ELIXIR nodes, Platforms, and Communities that would create an viable environment for data management know-how exchange and further capacity building.

Another important impact of the model also lies in recommending the funding of data management services, their sustainability and scalability. The basic framework suggested to be supported by ELIXIR, can be extended by personnel and technical elements funded from project eligible costs. It is worth noting that the role of the presented model is to pursue the effective utilisation of resources through a harmonised approach to all elements of the data life cycle reflected in data management.

8. Next Steps

The next major steps will be to make the model publicly available and promote it across ELIXIR Nodes. The starting point for data management in its breadth and depth is the [RDMkit](#) website which offers the most convenient model localization. The publication of the model will be carried out in collaboration with WP3. Close collaboration with WP2 is expected, aiming to define the most suitable means for the dissemination and implementation of the model. The model can also serve as the foundation for developing a Data Management Service Operation Maturity model for the ELIXIR nodes.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable.

